

The Effect of Job Description and Job Stress on Performance of Employees with Employment Satisfaction as Intervening Variables in PT Bess Finance Medan

Elfira Ilany¹, Prihatin Lumbanraja², Muhammad Zarlis²

¹Postgraduate Students, Department of Management, Faculty of Economics and Business at Universitas Sumatera Utara, Indonesia

²Postgraduate Lecturer, Department of Management, Faculty of Economics and Business at Universitas Sumatera Utara, Indonesia

Corresponding Author: Elfira Ilany

ABSTRACT

PT. Bess Finance is a limited liability company engaged in consumer financing which already has many branch offices in various cities in Indonesia and has many employees, one of which is PT Bess Finance branch Kapten Muslim Medan along with its development there is a decrease in performance of employees caused by lack of satisfaction employee's work is due to unclear job description and pressures from leaders that make employees often experience job stress. The purpose of this study was to determine and analyze the effect of job description and job stress on performance of employees with employment satisfaction as intervening variable. This type of research is quantitative associative. The population of this study were 42 employees and the sample collection used a census sample, that is, all the population were 42 employees. Data analysis uses path analysis. Research results show that job description and job stress have a significant effect on performance of employees and employment satisfaction can be a variable that mediates the relationship between job description and job stress on performance of employees in PT Bess Finance Medan.

Keywords: Job Description, Job Stress, Performance of Employees, Employment Satisfaction

INTRODUCTION

In today's business world, it is required to create high employee performance for company development. The company must be able to build and improve performance within its environment, given the increasing competition, technological changes, globalization and other factors quickly. The success of the company is influenced by several factors, one of the important factors is human resources.

Sunyoto (2015) suggests that human resources are one of the most important factors in an organization or company, in addition to other factors such as assets and capital. The potential of any human resources that exist in the company must be able to be utilized properly so as to provide optimum output. The success of an organization is heavily influenced by the individual performance of its employees. Every organization or company will always strive to improve employee performance, with the expectation of what the company's goals will be achieved.

Performance is the output produced by the functions or indicators of a work or a profession in a particular time (Hamali, 2016). Performance is the result of work that has a strong relationship with the strategic objectives of the Organization, customer satisfaction and contributing to the

economy. Performance is about doing the work and results achieved from the work. Performance is all about what to do and how to work on it. Increasing employee performance determines the success in deploying one's person to behave in accordance with the rules that have been established to support the achievement of organizational objectives. Achieving organizational objectives will fail when employees in the organization do not carry out existing missions.

In improving the performance of its employees the company can take several ways for example by observing several things, among them are job descriptions and work stress. The main objective of the job description is to reduce the work dissatisfaction and the alienation of the recurring officers. Through job descriptions, organizations strive to increase employee productivity levels by enhancing their responsibilities and creating a sense of personal achievement (Davoudi & Allahyari, 2013). Not only a job description factor that is noticed by the company to improve employee performance, but the company should pay attention to the working stress factor. Stress work can be defined as a condition that arises from interactions between humans and jobs as well as characterised by human changes that compel them to deviate from their normal function of Beehr & Newman in (Akbar et al., 2016).

Occupational Stress is faced by almost all employees in the working environment. Workload and also work demands that must be completed in a short time will cause pressure on employees. Working stress can also be sourced from family stress. Lack of harmonized relationships in households or related problems with the family will certainly bring impact to the performance of employees in the workplace. The necessity of mastering technology in the company also becomes a source of stress for employees.

High job satisfaction shows that an organization has managed the needs of employees well through effective management. Employees will be satisfied in working if the aspects of the work and their individual support each other so that it can be said that the job satisfaction is related to the feeling of a person about the fun or not employee work.

With the job description, work literacy and employee alienation arising from repeated tasks can be reduced. With the rotation of work, working methods, training, problem solving and goal setting will greatly help employees in carrying out their duties and delivering good performance. Likewise with working stress, employees who are experiencing stress work (with notes can not respond) tend to be unproductive, lazy, ineffective and inefficient in doing their job and various attitudes that can harm the organization.

The company's attention to physical and nonphysical condition of employees in their work makes the employees feel aware and can make employees feel good job satisfaction so motivated to improve their performance. It is hoped that a company to always pay attention to its employees in order to always produce good performance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Job Description

According to Rivai (2004) The job description is the overall research summary of job information and the requirements of the implementation of an employee as a result of the analysis that contains the basic task of the job description. According to Nawawi (2008) the description of the work can also be defined as a result of job analysis or the process of collecting and processing information about a job, which is formulated in written form. According to Mathis & Jackson (2006) Job description is a process of mentioning the task, the responsibility of the type of the job field.

The tasks need to be clearly known what type, the responsibility of what should be held by the employee who will perform

the task, so that employees do not make mistakes with the clarity of work that the employee should be doing. While according to Pophal (2008), the work description is a written record of the responsibilities of a particular work. Based on the experts' opinion on the definition of work descriptions above, it can be concluded that the work description is information about the job information about the duties and responsibilities of a job.

2.2 Job Stress

Stress has different meanings for each individual. Everyone's ability is diverse in overcoming the amount, intensity, type and duration of stress. People are easier to talk about tension than stress. Stress is something that concerns interactions between individuals and the environment, namely the interaction between stimulation and response. So stress is the consequence of every action and environmental situation that poses excessive psychological and physical demands on a person.

Stress is not something strange or that is not related to the normal circumstances that occur in normal people or not all stress are negative. The stress that employees suffer from the environment they face will affect the performance and satisfaction of their work. So management needs to improve the quality of organizational environment for employees. By decreasing the stress experienced by employees will certainly also improve health in the body of the organization.

According to (Handoyo, 2001:63) defining stress is external demands about a person, such as objects in the environment or a stimulus that is objectively dangerous. Stress is also commonly interpreted as an unpleasant stress, tension or distraction that comes from outside oneself.

2.3 Performance of Employees

Hasibuan (2007) expressed performance is a work done by employees who are usually used as a basis for the assessment of employees or organizations.

Good performance is a step to achieving the objectives of the Organization. So it is necessary to strive to improve performance. But this is not easy because many factors affect the high low of one's performance.

Simamora (2006) expressed performance refers to the achievement rate of the task-the task that formed an employee's work. Performance reflects how well employees meet the requirements of a job. Rivai (2004) expressed performance is a real behavior that is shown by everyone as an achievement of work produced by employees in accordance with their role in the company. Employee performance is crucial in the company's effort to achieve its objectives. From some of these descriptions, it can be suggested that performance is the real work that a person has accomplished in carrying out the duties given to him in accordance with the criteria and objectives set by the organization.

2.4 Employment Satisfaction

Reality shows that positive feelings encourage creativity, improve problem-solving and decision-making. Positive feelings also improve task persistence and attract more help and support from co-workers. Job satisfaction refers to the general attitude of an individual to his work. A person with a high level of job satisfaction shows a positive attitude towards his work and conversely when an employee is unhappy with his or her work, the employee will show a negative attitude towards his job.

Handoko (1992) suggests that work satisfaction is a pleasant or unpleasant emotional state for employees to view their work.

RESEARCH METHODS

3.1 Types and Properties of Research

This research uses quantitative associative, which is more research based on data that can be calculated to produce an assessment (Sugiyono, 2014). Associative research is a study to test the relationship or influence of free variables against bonded variables.

3.2 Place and Time Research

This research was conducted in PT. Bess Finance, Jl. Kapten Muslim Medan. Research starts from March to July 2018.

3.3 Population and Samples

The population is a generalization area consisting of objects and subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics applied by researchers to study and then withdrawn (Rusiadi, 2015:30). The population in this study was the employee of PT. Bess Finance Medan as much as 42 people.

When the subject is less than 100 it is taken all this research to use the

population/census samples. Based on the above definition, the authors take the population, which is 42 people to be used as samples.

3.4 Data Analysis Methods

The data analysis method in this study uses path analysis.

RESULT

Test Partial Effect Significance (t Test)

Table 1 and Table 2 present a regression coefficient value, as well as a statistical value of t for partial effect testing.

Table 1. Job Description, Job Stress on Employment Satisfaction Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	19.170	5.314		3.607	.001
	Job Description	.415	.102	.509	4.083	.000
	Job Stress	-.391	.136	-.358	-.2872	.007

a. Dependent Variable: Employment Satisfaction
Source: Processed Data

According to table 1, a double linear regression equation is obtained as follows.

$$Z = 0.509X_1 - 358X_2$$

Based on the results in table 1, unknown:

1. The coefficient value of the job description is 0.509, which is positive value. This means that the job description has a positive effect on employment satisfaction. Unknown value $t_{count} 4.083 > t_{table} 2.02$ and

$sig 0.000 < 0.05$, the job description is positive and significant to employment satisfaction.

2. The coefficient value of the job stress is -0.358, which is negative value. This means that the job stress has a negative effect on employment satisfaction. Unknown value $t_{count} -0.2872 < t_{table} 2.02$ and $sig 0.007 < 0.05$, the job stress is positive and significant to employment satisfaction.

Table 2. Job Description, Job Stress, Employment Satisfaction on Performance of Employees Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	10.822	3.631		2.980	.005
	Job Description	.215	.078	.408	2.768	.009
	Job Stress	-.234	.088	-.325	-2.650	.012
	Employment Satisfaction	.176	.065	.272	2.721	.010

a. Dependent Variable: Performance of Employees
Source: Processed Data

According to Table 2, a double linear regression equation is obtained as follows.

$$Y = 0.408X_1 - 0.325X_2 + 0.272Z$$

Based on the results in table 1, unknown:

The coefficient value of the job description is 0.408, which is positive value. Unknown value $t_{count} 2.768 > t_{table} 2.02$ and $sig 0.009$

< 0.05 , the job description is positive and significant to performance of employees.

The coefficient value of the job stress is -0.325, which is positive value. Unknown value $t_{count} -2.650 > t_{table} 2.02$ and $sig 0.012 < 0.05$, the job stress is positive and significant to performance of employees.

1. The coefficient value of the employment satisfaction is 0.272, which is positive value. Unknown value $t_{count} 2.721 > t_{table} 2.02$ and $sig 0.010 < 0.05$, the employment satisfaction is positive and significant to performance of employees.

Total Effect

Total effect is the amount of direct effect coupled with indirect effect. To calculate the total effect can be seen in Table 3 as follows:

Table 3. Total Effect Value

No.	Effect	Direct Effect	Indirect Effect	Total Effect
1	Job Description to Performance of Employees	0.408	$0.509 \times 0.272 = 0.138448$	$0.138448 + 0.408 = 0.546448$
2	Job Stress to Performance of Employees	-0.325	$-0.358 \times 0.272 = 0.097276$	$0.097276 + 0.325 = 0.422276$

Source: Processed Data

According to Table 3 above we can know that the value of the job description (X_1) effect on performance of employees (Y) through employment satisfaction (Z) is 0.546448, and job stress (X_2) effect on performance of employees (Y) through employment satisfaction (Z) is 0.422276.

Known job description significantly effect employment satisfaction and significant employment satisfaction effect performance of employees, then employment satisfaction is a variable that mediates the relationship between job description to performance of employees.

Known job stress significantly effect employment satisfaction and significant employment satisfaction effect performance of employees, then employment satisfaction is a variable that mediates the relationship between job stress to performance of employees.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

Research results show that job description and job stress have a significant effect on performance of employees and employment satisfaction can be a variable that mediates the relationship between job description and job stress on performance of employees in PT Bess Finance Medan.

Based on research studies that have been conducted then the advice of researchers are:

1. We should party from PT. Bess Finance to further improve the description of the job more detailed and specific and clear in directing employees to perform their duties and responsibilities especially for employees who are just starting to work so

that the company's objectives can be more accomplished.

2. Should the parties of PT. Bess Finance not pressure-pressure to employees in the work that does not make employees feel uncomfortable in working so that the company's objectives can be achieved by making a claim to employees that lead to the success of the company by providing training and guidance to the employees and not very often scold employees who do not reach the targets that have been determined by the company because it will affect the physical and psychic employees.

3. We recommend PT. Bess Finance a employment satisfaction to employees by providing salaries that are able to compete with other Finance and bonuses that can improve employee satisfaction such as overtime wage added incentives that are suitable to the performance given by employees and give a bankruptcy reward employees who excel so that employees feel the satisfaction of working.

4. Performance of employees should be more optimized again by looking at the fundamentals of being an employee's barriers in raising performance such as job descriptions, job stress and employment satisfaction.

5. This research can also be used as a reference for subsequent studies relating to concepts or theories that support knowledge and that is the limitation of this research on job descriptions, job stress, job satisfaction and performance of employees. In addition, other researchers should examine other variables such as training, leadership style and motivation by combining other studies

with this research, so that the relationship is known to the various variables that can measure employee performance.

REFERENCES

1. Akbar Syed Waqar, Muhamad Yousuf, Naeem Ui haq, & Ahmed imbran Hunjua. (2016). *Impact of Employee Empowerment on Job Satisfaction An Empirical Analysis of Pakistani Service Industry*. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business*, 2 (11):680-685.
2. Davoudi, S, M, M., & Allahyari, M. (2013). *Effect of Job Organization on Job Performance among Operating Staffs in Manufacturing Companies*. 3:136-139.
3. Hasibuan, Malayu S.P. (2007). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Perusahaan*. Bandung: PT. Bumi Aksa.
4. Hamali, Arif Yusuf. (2016). *Pemahaman Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Yogyakarta: CAPS.
5. Handoko, Hani T. (1992). *Manajemen Personalia dan SDM*. Jakarta: BPFE.
6. Handoyo, S. (2001). *Stres Pada Masyarakat Surabaya*. *Jurnal Insan Media Psikologi* 3 (12): 61-74.
7. Mathis & Jackson. (2006). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia. Edisi Pertama, Cetakan Pertama*. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
8. Nawawi, Hadari. (2008). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Untuk Bisnis yang Kompetitif. Cetakan Keempat*. Penerbit Gadjah Mada.
9. Pophal, Lin. (2008). *Human Resources Book*. Jakarta: Prenada.
10. Rivai, Veithzal. (2004). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia untuk Perusahaan*. Jakarta: Raja Grafindo.
11. Rusiadi. (2015). *Metode Penelitian Manajemen, Akuntansi, dan Ekonomi Pembangunan*. Medan: USU Press.
12. Simamora, Henry. (2006). *Manajemen Sumberdaya Manusia*. Yogyakarta: Sekolah Tinggi Ilmu Ekonomi YKPN.
13. Sugiyono. (2014). *Metode Penelitian Bisnis Pendekatan Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D. Cetakan Ke Enam Belas*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
14. Sunyoto, Danang. (2015). *Manajemen dan Pengembangan Sumber Daya Manusia*. Yogyakarta: CAPS.

How to cite this article: Ilany E, Lumbanraja P, Zarlis M. The effect of job description and job stress on performance of employees with employment satisfaction as intervening variables in PT Bess Finance Medan. *International Journal of Research and Review*. 2020; 7(6): 298-303.
